

Entrepreneurship Education: A Literature Review To Educational Practice

By

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Introduction

There is a latent risk that, if comprehensive and concerted policies are not implemented, values of inequality and the reduction of progress in societies will persist and increase, given the social isolation caused by the pandemic in 2020-2021 that has caused and continues to impact economic activities, modified the forms of work, education, and others, worldwide. Concerning work, the International Labor Organization (ILO) indicates that this sector has been rapidly transformed and adapted to the context, with different modalities coexisting (on-site, distance or mixed); however, the group of permanent workers has been reduced, and the number of independent and unemployed workers has increased, which is attributed to the scarcity of formal jobs. In the same situation is the educational service, where face-to-face classes were affected and forced to use various strategies to implement distance, virtual or remote education; however, inequalities in the conditions of connectivity, equipment, and technological capabilities have deepened the gap in access to education, in addition to the economic lack of families (ILO, 2020, 2021).

Regarding learning in entrepreneurship, in Latin America, Colombia applies an educational curriculum that develops the Culture for Entrepreneurship as a learning area in schools and has issued an orientation guide to create companies and contribute positively as a worker, but it does not reach the training proposals or how to integrate it with other areas. It also recognizes several types of entrepreneurship, the entrepreneurial, which it defines as the set of educational experiences aimed at proposing business initiatives and promoting beneficial projects for the school (Hinestroza et al. (Hinestroza et al., 2018).

In the measurement carried out by the National Institute of Statistics and Informatics (INEI) of Peru, regarding education and work, during 2020, it warns that 64.5 % of adolescents between 14 and 17 years old dedicate their time to study, while 19.8 % dedicate their time to study and work, 6 % only work and 9.7 % neither study nor work; these values are discouraging compared to 2019, because the percentage of adolescents who dedicate their time exclusively to study decreased by 9%, but the percentage of adolescents who study and

at the same time work increased, in addition to those whom neither study nor work increased (INEI, 2021).

In the Peruvian education system, the Ministry of Education (MINEDU) provides for the training of students with capacities and skills to create and sustain entrepreneurial activities through the area of Education for Work, which develops the competence of managing productive or service entrepreneurship projects in high school, so that upon graduation they can start entrepreneurial activities and insert themselves with relevance in the labor market, and contribute to the local economy and productivity, thus reducing unemployment. (MINEDU, 2016).

Given the above, the article aims to conduct a literature review of how to educate in entrepreneurship and highlight educational practices, strategies and programs that strengthen entrepreneurial skills in people; research published since 2018 is considered.

Methodology

A qualitative documentary approach is applied, based on the theoretical review of scientific information sources registered in the Scopus database, Dialnet, Redalyc, Scielo, Latindex and university repositories; the sources were selected considering journal articles, books in digital format, graduate work and conference papers, through keywords such as entrepreneurship education, entrepreneur, and experiences related to gender, entrepreneur, development of entrepreneurial skills, entrepreneurial skills, and other topics related to the objective.

Entrepreneurship for entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship, developed in students, is defined as a competence that provides them with capabilities that allow them to implement innovative, productive projects that transcend and position themselves in their environment; competence acquired at school as part of their comprehensive training where the student strengthens their entrepreneurial spirit while reinforcing their knowledge and skills, it is also important to indicate that an entrepreneur has a creative attitude, effective communication and opts for teamwork; in addition to converting a business idea into a project and opportunity to do business according to their context (Aldana et al., 2020).

The characteristics of an entrepreneur, according to a study conducted on young people between 18 and 25 years of age, indicate that in the first place is the desire to be one's boss, then the significant influence of the family, since it motivates the young person to undertake, likewise, when young people are related to entrepreneurial activities, they enhance their entrepreneurial character, age is an important variable in the formation of an entrepreneurial person. Therefore, it is important to generate strategies so that young people in educational institutions can develop these entrepreneurial skills, and therefore, it is important to generate strategies so that young people in educational institutions can develop their entrepreneurial character (Valenzuela-Keller et al., 2021).

Entrepreneurship education

Entrepreneurship is a way to relate the student to the business environment, which favors their social development and vocational orientation; therefore, the need to include in the school curriculum; many countries claim to consider entrepreneurship training, however, none have implemented it at all levels, nor in all students, in the Spanish educational system there are deficiencies in the strategies and programs that implement entrepreneurship as a

competence driven by the school and family, obtaining low learning achievements in entrepreneurship, so it requires improvement in its approach and strategies (Caballero-García et al., 2019).

Entrepreneurship competence can be measured by considering four components: observing the context and recognizing opportunities, proposing creative solutions, generating resistance to frustration, persevering in entrepreneurship and promoting its realization, characteristics that can be valued in a person as an entrepreneur (Guillén-Tortajada et al., 2020).

On the other hand, a sample of secondary school teachers from European Union countries (Greece, Spain, Italy and Belgium) emphasize that entrepreneurship training is important; they report having worked on motivation, creativity and learning through experience; however, they make little use of mobile equipment in school activities, the study concludes that training actions are needed for teachers specifically in the development of learning guides and articulation with other curricular disciplines (Prendes et al., 2020).

Entrepreneurship education has the purpose of activating the economy and being important for the development of rural areas; therefore, the entrepreneurship education program applied in the northern region of Norway offers seminars on business creation and business ideas to students, whom mentors accompany, then plan the venture, define a business model, identify related partners, always accompanied by experts, and finally, the students present the proposal to a panel of entrepreneurs; the program was relevant and impactful for the participants, they concluded that it is sustainable. However, the limitation of the study is that it is a single study conducted in a Norwegian Arctic setting.

Studies on entrepreneurship with university informants conclude that the “motivation for entrepreneurship” would be influenced by elements centered on the person, such as being self-sufficient, the desire to ascend and increase their economy, the addition of a trade or profession, or by external elements such as the economic situation of the country or family history. They also identified skills necessary for entrepreneurship: openness to change, positive attitude towards failure, willingness to persevere, self-evaluation, autonomy, and proactive and ethical management (Castelao et al., 2015).

Since 2006, Colombia has been implementing educational policies for entrepreneurial education, achieving changes in the thinking of basic, middle and higher education graduates; the state regulates the “culture of entrepreneurship,” encouraging the generation of evidence from the student’s reality, which should materialize in the start of an enterprise, in response to the solution of a problem; however, in rural contexts, teachers in charge of these training processes do not know how to adapt the curriculum to the needs of their community (Pérez, 2021).

The concept of education in entrepreneurship, which the Colombian educational system assumes, that form productive people providing them with citizenship, labor and business skills, for such purpose, implements a program to carry out a business and considers the entire process, i.e., from the generation of the idea and the execution of the plan, in the program a multidisciplinary team of advisors is required (Segura-Barón et al., 2019)..

The Business Management career in university higher education in Ecuador implemented plans for the development of independent competencies, being necessary to formulate curricula where competencies are articulated and integrated, promoting the

teaching of creativity, innovation, collaborative work, inquiry, and not considering terminal courses aimed at planning, project design and statistics (Cobo et al., 2020).

In Peru, 53% of university students in the Administration program demonstrated a moderate level of entrepreneurial capacity, i.e., students can act with initiative, perseverance and self-confidence; for perception by gender, the study found that there are no differences between the entrepreneurial capacity of women and men (Midolo et al., 2021).

Entrepreneurs have their characteristics, and a study of entrepreneurs who run businesses indicates that gender difference is not relevant or creates difficulties for women who have already succeeded in entrepreneurship; it also concludes that the difficulties for women's entrepreneurship are more related to the social culture and the environment (Yurrebaso et al., 2020).

For the performance of teachers in the area of Education for Work (EPT) in an educational institution in the department of Apurimac in Peru, a study concludes that they have difficulties in developing management competencies that include entrepreneurial skills, oriented to market research, planning, marketing and other activities; they are also unaware of appropriate active strategies and methodologies; they consider that few hours are assigned to the area and that there is a lack of environments equipped to carry out productive projects (Cruzata et al., 2021).

Characteristics of education in times of pandemic

Because of the health crisis from 2020 to 2021, the governing institution of the education sector issued official documents to regulate the provision of services according to epidemiological and territorial conditions, establishing three types of services, including distance or non-face-to-face education, i.e., students do not share physical space with teachers or among peers (MINEDU, 2021). In non-face-to-face education, intensive use is made of technological resources, which requires that students and teachers acquire digital skills to ensure their proper use; however, in the context of the pandemic, there was evidence of low teaching performance attributed to the low level in the use and management of technology (Huamán et al., 2021).

A study conducted in Turkey on distance education service records low student participation, unmotivated pedagogical activities, lack of equipment and the perception that classes are inefficient; also, students show low motivation to respond and participate in classes; the research recommends that teachers must improve their technological performance (Tas et al., 2021).

Likewise, teachers and students experienced a diversity of problems, basically in three aspects: lack of internet and computer, technical staff and technological instructor, in addition, lack of opportunities for the use of online applications, internet use, and access to planning and evaluation raised by the teacher, also the collaboration of parents was reduced; in response, strategies and initiatives have been generated to overcome the barriers. However, it is necessary to investigate the levels of learning under these conditions of educational service (ÜdoÖzüdoğru, 2021).

Entrepreneurship education in Peru

Among the didactic strategies applied in the area of Education for Work (EPT), the following stand out: design thinking, also known as entrepreneurial thinking design that influences learning for project management in high school students, as well as entrepreneurial

competencies in individuals, in a similar way grants greater ability to create and activate entrepreneurial alertness in students, a research-validated its use in American schools (Pratomo et al., 2021). Similarly, it contributes to the use of technological tools, Canvas business models, virtual classrooms and others, which integrated with didactic strategies, allowed the development of competencies focused on entrepreneurship, specifically business initiatives and business models on the internet (García-Ruiz et al., 2020).

Entrepreneurship and gender

The participation of women in entrepreneurial activities is growing in Latin America; however, some factors do not favor the access and development of women entrepreneurs; among them, they point out the country's culture, politics and economic freedom, being the governmental support programs that do promote it (Sansores & Navarrete, 2020).

In addition, women have few opportunities for entrepreneurship since they assume household responsibility and raise children, usually at a young age and even without completing high school. This "culture of patriarchy" still prevails in Latin America. For example, in studies conducted in Ecuadorian communities, women are dedicated to their entrepreneurial activities by complying with household activities and trying to get the consent of their partner, in the best of cases; to empower women it is necessary to implement public policies and education in entrepreneurship from school (Ordóñez et al., 2019).

Although women entrepreneurs face significant challenges to entrepreneurship, among which stand out: labor discrimination, exclusion from the male environment, lack of support and the responsibility of the family, current research shows advances in the empowerment of female entrepreneurship, with the family being the primary support to help boost their businesses and find opportunities in the labor market, causing changes in the environment and making it more equitable (Flores-Novelo et al., 2021).

A study based on interviews with women entrepreneurs in Seville and Newcastle found that the participants consider important the intervention in business networks, women's societies, and academic activities in business and finance; however, the entrepreneurship policies developed in their regions are unknown to them. Therefore, the policies do not respond to their interests and needs; it also concludes that in female entrepreneurship, families directly influence their decisions, in addition to requiring funding, support and project grants, gender is a barrier (Suárez-Ortega & Fariña-Sánchez, 2021).

In view of the experiences recorded and studies, it is attributed that a competency-based education in entrepreneurship is relevant for women, specifically in the period of professional training, because it strengthens entrepreneurial skills and competencies, which contributes to labor and economic empowerment, as well as to their growth and business distinction; however, studies are required regarding the factors that determine or favor these skills and others aimed at knowing their aspirations, actions and reflections (Garavito et al., 2021).

Conclusion

An entrepreneurial education is important when it improves people's skills and behaviors and can have a positive impact, depending on how it is carried out. Therefore, it is necessary to highlight and prioritize entrepreneurial teaching and learning in secondary and higher education, implement and modernize workshops, and train teachers; studies show that

it influences the entrepreneurial future of students and their entrepreneurial attitude (Bravo et al., 2021).

Entrepreneurial competencies comprise business issues, planning, organization, supply, demand, investment, advertising, and technological tools, and all have the purpose of developing the entrepreneurial potential of people; however, Hebles et al. (2019) propose that training programs in entrepreneurship consider strategies with learning experiences in entrepreneurial workshops and relate to them since they influence them positively in consolidating entrepreneurial attitudes. Also, managing entrepreneurial projects considers business plans that should materialize in creating a family or commercial enterprise.

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